

Sufficient Choice of Steel Material for Bridge Bearings to Avoid Brittle Fracture

Determination of correction functions

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ABSTRACT

Usually, steel structures are designed for the high layer region of the steel toughness-temperature. To account for reduced toughness properties in the temperature transition range, additional safety checks, rooted in fracture mechanics considerations, are necessary. These checks allow a sufficient choice of steel material to avoid brittle fracture.

Given this context, recommendations were outlined in 2011 to regulate the suitable selection of steel grades for bearing components. However, these proposals are no longer fully aligned with more recent insights. Consequently, the German Centre for Rail Traffic Research has announced a research project with the aim to define a proposal for expanding the regulatory framework concerning appropriate material selection to avoid brittle fracture in bridge bearings.

Keywords: bridge bearings, brittle fracture, choice of material, correction function

1 INTRODUCTION

The Federal Republic of Germany currently bears the responsibility for the construction and upkeep of approximately 39,000 bridges within the federal trunk road network. Operating as a subsidiary of Deutsche Bahn AG, DB Netz AG is additionally tasked with the maintenance of over 25,000 railway bridges of diverse designs across Germany (1).

In preserving the longevity and operational efficiency of these structures, bearings play a crucial role in maintaining stability. These bearings facilitate proper load distribution from the superstructure to the substructure while enabling controlled movement of the superstructure with minimal constraint.

2 STATE OF RESEARCH

2.1 Material selection for bridge bearings

The application of DIN EN 1337 (2) in tandem with the corresponding parts of DIN EN 1993 in designing bridge bearings and their components is leading to an increasing trend of employing large plate thicknesses, especially for bridges with long spans. However, these plate thicknesses exceed the prescribed application limits outlined in the national appendix of DIN EN 1993-2 (3). Moreover, compliance with the regulations specified in DIN EN 1993-1-10 (4) regarding material toughness and through-thickness properties cannot be applied without additional modifications. Consequently, these standards cannot be directly applied for the choice of material for bridge bearings without supplementary information.

Given this context, a recommendation was formulated in 2011 for the regulation of an appropriate steel grade selection for bearing components (see (5)). Before the research project on which this contribution is based was called out the mentioned recommendation had only been made available as a technical bulletin. Since July 2023, it is integrated into guideline 804 of the German railway. Although, recent findings (see (6), (7), (8)) have shown that certain bridge bearing components are subjected to high fatigue loads which necessitate consideration in the structural design, material selection and calculations. Therefore, the German Centre for Rail Traffic Research called a research project with the aim to define a proposal to expand the standardization in order to implement a sufficient choice of steel material for bridge bearings to avoid brittle fracture.

2.2 Principle according to EN 1993-1-10

To establish regulations that cater to the specific requirements of bridge bearings, the well-established and globally accepted concept of toughness verification, based on material selection rules, is applied in civil and bridge engineering. Expanding to this approach, the intention is to develop a tabular verification format, akin to EN 1993-1-10, designed to suit the specific and distinctive conditions of the bridge bearing sector. The following summaries provide a foundational understanding of the verification concept, while a detailed explanation can be found in (4) and (9).

The concept relies on fracture mechanics and correlational considerations, integrating the steel manufacturer's toughness assurance derived from notch impact test values. This method ensures adequate toughness in an application-specific manner, with a reasonable time investment and minimal potential for errors. It eliminates the necessity for fracture mechanical investigations in each individual case, which would demand considerable expertise and time.

Concretely, the material selection is guided by Table 2.1 in EN 1993-1-10 (4), employing the relationship outlined in Eq. (1). The impact of T_{Ed} is formed by additive temperature components, which consider effects from ambient temperature, stress, strain rate, component geometry, as well as assumed crack damage, collectively exerting a negative impact on the material's toughness transition temperature. On the resistance side, material toughness is encompassed, expressed by the notch impact toughness. The summands are summarized as given below.

$$T_{mdr} + \Delta T_{\sigma} + \Delta T_R + \Delta T_{\dot{\epsilon}} + \Delta T_{\epsilon_{cf}} \geq (T_{27J} - 18^{\circ}C) + \Delta T_{27J} \quad (1)$$

- T_{mdr} describes the component temperature
- ΔT_{σ} describes the fracture mechanical influences
- ΔT_R represents an element of safety
- $\Delta T_{\dot{\epsilon}}$ takes high strain rates into account
- $\Delta T_{\epsilon_{cf}}$ captures effects of cold forming
- ΔT_{27J} describes the influence of material inhomogeneity on toughness

The temperature shifts due to increased strain rates and cold forming are not included in the tabulated values of permissible product thicknesses and therefore, if consideration is necessary, must be explicitly determined on a case-by-case basis. The corresponding formulas can be found in the mentioned standard.

3 FACTORS INFLUENCING THE BRITTLE FRACTURE DESIGN OF SPHERICAL BEARINGS

Brittle fracture failure can be exacerbated by various influences. In order to apply a determination of these influencing factors to the brittle fracture design of spherical bearings, it was investigated which factors favouring brittle fracture can be identified as significant in the field of railway bridge bearing constructions. In a further step, it was also elucidated in which order of magnitude these

factors can occur in practice and corresponding proposals will be made regarding which design principles of the verification format according to EN 1993-1-10 (4) can be retained and which factors may require modification.

For this purpose, the basic framework conditions of the influencing parameters were initially considered based on general material characteristics. In connection with this, determinations were made as to whether different boundary conditions should be applied in bridge bearing constructions than those on which EN 1993-1-10 (4) is based. Subsequently, an examination of the characteristic values of fatigue stresses was carried out.

Similarly, the elements of the temperature verification equation Eq. (1) were examined for their reception of the specifications made in (4) and (10) regarding the topic of bridge bearing constructions. It was described which parameters can be transferred to the relevant brittle fracture design scenario and which factors, on the other hand, require modification.

Table 1 provides a summary of the developed parameters of the temperature verification equation according to (4). In this, it is illustrated which parameters, in their application to bridge bearing constructions, exhibit modifications compared to the assumptions underlying EN 1993-1-10 (4). On the action side, the variable of temperature shift due to radiation losses ΔT_r is already included in the specified values of the component temperature T_{mdr} .

Table 1: Parameters of the temperature verification equation

parameters of the verification equation		EN 1993-1-10 (4)	bridge bearings in railway construction
T_{Rd}	$(T_{27J} - 18^\circ C)$	correlations according to Wallin (11) and Sanz (12)	
	ΔT_{27J}	consideration according to $\Delta T_{27J} = 12,9 * \tanh(2,1 * \ln(t) - 7,5) + 12,8$ depending on the material thickness	
Δ	T_{mdr}	according to table NA.A1 (13)	according to table NA.A1 (13): $-30^\circ C$
	ΔT_σ	type of notch: semi-elliptical surface crack	
manufacturing control: visual / dye penetrant testing		manufacturing control: ultrasonic testing	
initial crack size according to $a_0 = \begin{cases} 0,5 * \ln\left(1 + \frac{t}{t_0}\right) & \text{for } t < 15 \text{ mm} \\ 0,5 * \ln\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) & \text{for } t \geq 15 \text{ mm} \end{cases}$		initial crack size to be determined in the course of the research project	
ΔT_R	$+7^\circ C$		
$\Delta T_{\dot{\varepsilon}}$	consideration according to $\Delta T_{\dot{\varepsilon}} = -\frac{1440 - f_y(t)}{550} * \left(\ln \frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0}\right)^{1,5}$ with $\Delta T_{\dot{\varepsilon}} = 0^\circ C$ for $\dot{\varepsilon} \leq 1 * 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	generally not applied $\Delta T_{\dot{\varepsilon}} = 0^\circ C$	
$\Delta T_{\varepsilon_{cf}}$	consideration according to $\Delta T_{\varepsilon_{cf}} = 0$ for $\varepsilon_{cf} \leq 2 \%$ $\Delta T_{\varepsilon_{cf}} = -3 * \varepsilon_{cf}$ for $\varepsilon_{cf} > 2 \%$	generally not applied $\Delta T_{\varepsilon_{cf}} = 0^\circ C$	

4 NOTCH GEOMETRY AND CRACK PROPAGATION

As already mentioned, the concept of brittle fracture relies on fracture mechanics and correlational considerations. The starting point for this is the assumption of a cracked component, where the assumed incompleteness is considered as a sharp crack at the location of the highest geometric stress concentration.

Depending on the crack development, various types of cracks with different geometries are differentiated (see, for example, (14)). To enable a specific analysis for the respective application, such as the present topic of bridge bearings, it is consequently necessary to define the corresponding crack configuration. After considerations regarding the detailed geometry and crack size, the cyclic design scenario is thereupon examined. Based on the cyclic loads, taking into account material-specific conditions as well as individual external influences, the crack propagation is then determined.

4.1 FE simulations to calculate crack propagation

The crack propagation calculations use as an input the initial crack size highlighted in *Table 1* with $t_0 = 1 \text{ mm}$ and the product thickness t in [mm]. This assumption needs to be verified in the further course of the research project through the conducted large-scale component tests. Similarly, the ratio given in *Eq. (2)* is assumed for the semi-elliptical surface crack.

$$\frac{a}{c} = 0,4 \quad (2)$$

a crack depth
 c half the crack width

Further, the safety assessment to prevent brittle fracture is based on the fracture mechanics parameter known as the K-value. The stress intensity factor K_I , more precisely the correction functions Y_I and M_K , can be obtained from the literature for many applications, see e.g. (10), (15) and (16). Nevertheless, there are, notwithstanding reference to sources other than those listed here, numerous geometries and loading configurations for which no formulas exist for determining the stress intensity factor.

Where sufficiently verified correction functions for determining the relevant stress intensity factor are available for the investigated bearing details, the created FE models are compared with analytical calculations during the calculation and simulation. While for the bearing component of the anchor plate, hand calculation formulas according to *Raju and Newman* (15) can be used for this comparison, it is necessary for the other test specimen to determine corresponding correction functions individually depending on their respective geometry and loading situation.

4.2 Determination of the correction functions

To identify the critical location of the considered bearing details regarding brittle component failure, FE calculations are initially performed on undamaged simulation models. Thus, the location of the highest geometric stress concentration can be clearly determined in each specific case. Some results for this are shown in *Figure 1* and *Figure 2*.

For the crack opening mode of Mode I, the following formulation *Eq. (3)* arises depending on the external load as well as the crack and component geometry.

$$K_I = \sigma * \sqrt{\pi * a} * F(a)_I \quad \text{in } [N/mm^{3/2}] \text{ or } [MPa\sqrt{m}] \quad (3)$$

σ external load
 a crack size
 $F(a)_I$ dimensionless correction function (here for mode I)

Figure 1. Highest geometric stress concentration on the rotationally symmetrical upper part of the bearing

Figure 2. Highest geometric stress concentration on the lower part of the bearing

Hence, it becomes evident that a linear relationship exists between the applied nominal stress and the resulting stress intensity factor. Therefore, *Eq. (3)* in the computational model can be based on a nominal stress of 1 MPa , upon which the corresponding stress intensity can be determined based on an individual stress level. Ensuing, the magnitude of the load is to be chosen such that the loading conditions depicted in the large-scale component tests result in a nominal stress of 1 MPa along the component cross-section in the plane of the crack. The result of the sampled normal stress obtained from the models is exemplified for an axisymmetric upper bearing part in *Fig. 3*.

Following the determination of the required load for each bearing detail, calculations are carried out on the model with the introduced initial defect gradually increased according to *Eq. (3)*, while applying these loads. The actual component geometry can thus be kept constant, while the parameters of the crack depth a and half-crack width c within a predetermined parameter space, covering a pre-determined number of calculation steps, increase with each new calculation.

In each calculation step, the results of the stress intensity factor K_I are tabulated. By rearranging *Eq. (3)*, it is possible to make a statement about the dimensionless correction function. The values of the correction functions obtained this way, depending on an increasing crack depth, are then plotted on a diagram. To determine a suitable regression line that best explains the calculated values, in a next step, an appropriate polynomial or power function is to be evaluated. The determination coefficient R^2 , also determined in the same process, is furthermore a metric that indicates how much variation can be explained by the present regression model. R^2 ranges between zero and one, where the value one indicates an optimal explanation of the data.

Fig. 3. Normal stress along the cut surface - a) in crack plane; b) in crack plane, elevation

To verify the correctness of this procedure, the geometries of the anchor plate are initially considered and the obtained results are compared with the analytical calculations of the correction functions according to (15). Fig. 4 illustrates, in blue, the course of the correction function obtained through numerical simulation for an anchor plate, compared to the correction function determined through manual calculation, represented in orange. Up to a crack depth of approximately 10 mm, both functions run almost identically, with the slight deviation averaging below 2,5%. Upon exceeding this crack depth, the correction function obtained through numerical calculation exhibits lower values. The average deviation from a crack depth of 10 mm onwards is approximately 11,5%.

Fig. 4. Regression line anchor plate

In each received dataset of computational simulations, a trend line in the form of a polynomial function is subsequently inserted. The degree of the polynomial is chosen so that the variation explained by the present regression model is as close as possible to its associated optimal value, defined as 1 by the coefficient of determination R^2 . For the anchor plates, a second-order

polynomial proved sufficient, as can be seen in *Fig. 4*. The regression line developed this way serve as regression lines in the subsequent crack growth simulations, representing the correction functions used to calculate the evolving crack progression. This approach is subsequently applied on the other bearing details for which the literature does not provide information regarding the decisive stress intensity factor.

4.3 Calculation of crack propagation

In the course of the research project, large-scale component tests are planned. In this context, the calculation of crack propagation is significant in that it allows determining the point in time when an initial crack introduced into a test specimen has grown to a certain crack size under dynamic loading. This specific crack size is such that no unstable crack growth can be detected in the specimen. Mathematically speaking, this means searching for the moment when the design value of the applied stress intensity factor is just smaller than the material's fracture toughness, i.e., *Eq. (4)* must just be satisfied.

$$K^*_{appl,d} < K_{mat,d} \quad (4)$$

$K^*_{appl,d}$ applied stress intensity factor
 $K_{mat,d}$ material's fracture toughness

The crack size is then determined, depending on

- the temperature to which the specific bearing detail under consideration in each individual case needs to be cooled to achieve brittle fracture after the initiation of the initial crack,
- the load applied in the dynamic test per load cycle,
- the incrementally set number of load cycles,
- and the initial crack size at the beginning of the dynamic load test.

This is the size to which the defect is allowed to grow maximally before unstable crack growth occurs, leading to the fracture of the test specimen, as per *Eq. (4)*.

For the calculation of crack propagation, taking into account the previously determined numerical correction function, the crack size that marks the termination of cyclic loading in the experiment for the anchor plate is a crack depth value of $a_d = 6,23 \text{ mm}$. Simultaneously assuming that the crack size ratio remains for a semi-elliptical surface crack according to *Eq. (2)*, the crack width is consequently $c = 15,58 \text{ mm}$.

To verify plausibility, the same procedure is applied using the analytical formulas of *Raju and Newman (15)*. The results can be seen in *Table 2*. As a comparison between manual and software-based methods reveals, the deviation of calculated crack sizes is minimal, with a maximum of 4,4% in the case of anchor plate 1. Thus, the numerical simulations are considered validated, and the same calculation method is applied to those bearing details for which no manual formulas are available in the literature for comparison.

For further illustration, *Fig. 5* depicts the crack depth plotted against the number of load cycles, illustrating the growth of the initial defect with an increasing number of applied load cycles. The path's trajectory indicates the exponentially increasing crack propagation leading to the specimen's failure. Emphasized is the crack size at which the design value of the applied stress intensity factor is just below the characteristic fracture toughness of the material. It is important to note that the attained crack size is crucial for the conclusion of dynamic loading in the tests.

Table 2: Crack sizes just before the start of unstable crack growth

no. of anchor plate	numerical simulation	Raju & Newman	initial crack size	crack size when dynamic test is stopped			
			a_0 [mm]	a_d [mm]	Δa_d [%]	c [mm]	Δc [%]
1	✓		3,00	6,23	4,4	15,58	4,4
		✓	3,00	5,97		14,92	
2	✓		3,00	6,18	3,9	15,44	3,8
		✓	3,00	5,95		14,87	
3	✓		1,4722	4,52	1,1	11,29	1,2
		✓	1,4722	4,47		11,16	

Fig. 5. Crack propagation anchor plate 1

5 SUMMARY

To formulate rules for appropriate material selection to prevent brittle fracture in bridge bearings within the ongoing research project of the German Centre for Rail and Traffic Research, influencing factors of brittle fracture were initially identified. Following this, fracture mechanics analyses were conducted to establish correction functions and estimate the stress intensity at crack tips. Actual component tests are scheduled in the upcoming months to validate the obtained results, simulating the brittle failure of bridge bearing components in a laboratory setting. Subsequently in-depth parameter studies seek to enable a thorough evaluation and enhanced comprehension of material behaviour and fracture mechanisms. The ultimate goal is to formulate a proposal for expanding the regulatory framework concerning appropriate material selection, with the specific aim of preventing brittle fracture in bridge bearings.

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